

Face Sketch Image Category Classification Using Bag of Words (BoW) Model

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Abstract: *Face sketch category classification (categorization) of via computer vision is still a complicated and difficult task due to the various properties of face components. This paper proposes the category classification of face sketch components (face shapes, hairs, left eyebrows, left eyes, noses and mouths) which are based on 2400 real face training data set for each components. This categorization analyzes the numerical properties of various image features and organizes data into categories. Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT), Speeded Up Robust Feature (SURF) descriptors, K-means clustering algorithm, Bag of Words (BoW) model and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier approaches are mainly used for image category classification process. This paper is particularly suited for the environment where law enforcement which facial composites are used mainly by police in their investigation of serious crimes and entertainment. With the advancement of information technology, the computerized face sketch category classification system should be used all over the countries. The datasets used in this system are China University Hong Kong (CUHK) face sketch datasets.*

Keywords: Category classification; Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT); Speeded Up Robust Feature (SURF) descriptors; K-means clustering algorithm; Bag of Words (BoW) model; Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier

1. INTRODUCTION

The human visual system is an interesting and amazing part of the body. This visual system is fast and precise. Only a glance can know what are in the scene, how far they are and what actions are taking place. This is because human has an incredible brain behind that optical system. The face is one of most important part of human beings to differentiate person's identity. [7] The number of digital images is growing extremely rapidly, and so is the need for their classification.

Classification includes a broad range of decision-theoretic approaches to the identification of images. All classification algorithms are based on the assumption that the image depicts one or more features and that each of these features belongs to one of several distinct and exclusive classes. As computers became more powerful and better algorithms were developed, automatic image classification has become accurate on smaller datasets with hundreds of categories and thousands of images.

Classification algorithm typically employ two phases of processing: training and testing. In the initial training phase, characteristic properties of typical image features are isolated and, based on these, a unique description of each classification category, i.e. training class is created. In the subsequent testing phase, these feature-space partitions are used to classify image features. Image category classification (categorization)

is the process of assigning a category label to an image under test.

2. PREPROCESSING

In the preprocessing step, all the face sketches are translated, rotated and scaled such that all of the face shapes are made with 150*195 pixels. Hairs are made with width 150 pixels. For face sketch construction case, when hairs can be composed with face shapes, such specific pixel skills are needed. Other sketch components such as left eyebrows, left eyes, noses and mouths are not defined with specific pixels. Their pixel values are not specific defined because left eyebrows, left eyes, noses and mouths image sets will be controlled position and scaling transitions in the face sketch construction task. So, the bigger and smaller problems of these pixel values are not needed to be considered. Right eyebrows and right eyes are not included in this classification because these two categories can be got from mirror algorithm for searching left eyebrows and left eyes.

2.1. Parallel Pool

Before beginning of the classification, this system must run on a parallel pool. Parallel pool can run another processes continuously after one process ends.

Several computer vision system toolbox functions support parallel computing using multiple matlab workers. There are 12 workers in a parallel pool. This system runs only 2 workers in a parallel pool for classification with two categories. Face shapes and left eyes will be in first group in a parallel pool for classification. The second classification group is hairs and left eyebrows. The final group is noses and mouths. The actual number of workers comprising the parallel pool might be fewer, if fewer workers or cores are available.

3. METHODOLOGY

In the methodology step, there are five stages for classification. The first stage is to set up image category sets. The second stage is to extract strongest features or grids from SIFT, SURF descriptor. The third stage is K-means clustering algorithm to reduce the strongest features. The fourth stage is Bag of Words model which containing vocabulary of visual words. The final stage is to train the image classifier (Support Vector Machine) with Bag of Words.

3.1. Set Up Image Category Sets

Organize and partition the images into training and test subsets. Use the imageDatastore function to store images to use for training an image classifier. [4] Organizing images into categories makes handling large sets of images much easier. It can be used the splitEachLabel function to split the images into training and test data. [1] Training Data Size Percent defines how much percentage of the data is kept for training. The remaining data is considered for validation. [5] This system of training data size percent is 30% and the remainder for testing.

Figure 1. Image Category Sets

3.2. Feature Extraction

In computer vision, speeded up robust features (SURF) is a patented local feature detector and descriptor. It can be used for tasks such as object recognition, image registration, classification or 3D reconstruction. It is partly inspired by the scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) descriptor. It can be

extracted features based on a feature detector, or can be defined a strongest feature or grid to extract feature descriptors. The grid method may lose fine-grained scale information. By default, the algorithm runs the 'grid' method. [3]

3.3. K-Means Clustering Algorithm

These strongest features or grids are then reduced through quantization of feature space using K-means clustering algorithm to obtain the visual words. K-means clustering algorithm is one of the simplest unsupervised learning algorithms. A cluster refers to a collection of data points aggregated together because of certain similarities. Mean in the K-means clustering algorithm refers to the averaging of the data. The algorithm iteratively groups the descriptors into *k* mutually exclusive clusters. The resulting clusters are compact and separated by similar characteristics. The number of clusters representing the number of features in the bag of features. This is the *k* parameter for the K-means clustering algorithm. It gives the best result when datasets are distinct or well separated from each other and forms the bag of features containing the vocabulary of visual words. Each cluster center represents a feature, or visual word. This system uses 500 clusters. The number of clusters of 500 with fraction of strongest features of 0.75 is proven to give best results.

3.4. Bag of Visual Words (BoW) Model

In image analysis, the bag-of-words model (BoW model, also known as bag-of-features) can be applied to achieve image classification, by treating image features as words. In textual document classification, a bag of words is a sparse vector of occurrence counts of words. The selected keywords forming the bag of words represents the vocabulary. [2]

In computer vision, a bag of visual words is a vector of occurrence counts of a vocabulary of local image features. The bag-of-visual-words technique relies on detection without localization. As the more increase of the datas, the datas cannot be performed only in RAMS. The most important analysis that BoW model can perform is that the more datas can be performed in Hard Disk but not in RAMs.

Figure 2. Create Bag-of-features

3.5. Support Vector Machine Classifier

The histograms of the training data are used to train a classifier called Support Vector Machine (SVM). Use the imageCategoryClassifier function predict method on a new image to determine its category. [6] The function trains a multiclass classifier using the error-correcting output codes (ECOC) framework with binary support vector machine (SVM) classifiers. Kernel function that the SVM classifier uses to map the training data into kernel space. The default kernel function is the dot product. The kernel function can be used in this system is Radial basis function (rbf), SVM_C, and SVM_RBF_Gamma. The equation for Support Vector Machine can be defined as

$$f(x) = \sum_i^N \omega_i k(x_i, y_i) + b$$

Where, N = size of training data,

ω_i = weight,

(x_i, y_i) is the pixel value of feature vectors,

The approximating function $f(x)$ is represented as a sum of N radial basis functions, and weighted by an appropriate coefficient ω_i .

Gaussian Radial Basis Function (rbf) defines kernel with a default scaling factor, gamma, of 1. Specify another value for gamma with the SVM_RBF_Gamma parameter. The equation for Radial Basis Function can be defined as

$$k(x_i, y_i) = e^{-r\|x_i, y_i\|^2}$$

Where, $k(x_i, y_i)$ = kernel function,

$r\|x_i, y_i\|$ = radial kernel,

(x_i, y_i) is the pixel value of feature vectors,

The equation for Support Vector Machine with Radial Basis Function can be defined as

$$f(x) = \sum_i^N \omega_i e^{-r\|x_i, y_i\|^2} + b$$

Where, N = size of training data,

ω_i = weight,

(x_i, y_i) is the pixel value of feature vectors,

$k(x_i, y_i)$ = kernel function,

$r\|x_i, y_i\|$ = radial kernel,

The approximating function $f(x)$ is represented as a sum of N radial basis functions, and weighted by an appropriate coefficient ω_i .

SVM_C : The C parameter tells the SVM classifier how much you want to avoid misclassifying each training example. This is why higher values make the classifier prone to outliers. If C is a scalar, it is automatically rescaled by $N/(2*N1)$ for the data points of group one and by $N/(2*N2)$ for the data points of group two, where N1 is the number of elements in group one, N2 is the number of elements in group two, and $N = N1 + N2$. This rescaling is done to take into account unbalanced groups, that is cases where N1 and N2 have very different values. If C is an array, then each array element is taken as a box constraint for the data point with the same index.

SVM_RBF_Gamma : The scaling factor in case that RBF kernel is used. Using a linear SVM kernel results into low system validation accuracy. While the Polynomial and RBF kernels give high performance.

3.6. Error-Correcting Output Codes (ECOC)

Error-Correcting Output Codes (ECOC) is one of the well-known techniques for multiclass classification which combines the outputs of binary based learners to predict the classes for multiclass data. A Fraction of strongest features, specified as the comma-separated pair consisting of Strongest Features and a value in the range [0,1]. The value represents the fraction of strongest features to use from each input class. This system uses 0.8 of strongest features. The output confusion matrix represents the analysis of the prediction. A perfect classification results in a normalized matrix containing 1s on the diagonal. An incorrect classification results fractional values.

Figure 3. Evaluate the quality of the classifier

Figure 4. Image Classification Process

This figure shows the different modules of the system and the interaction/data flow between these modules. The first stage is the feature extraction. In this system, it is extracted the SURF (speeded up robust features) features [2] are extracted for all the training images. SURF is partly inspired by the scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) descriptor. The strongest features are chosen based on a predefined percentage parameter inputted to the system.

These strongest features are then reduced through quantization of feature space using K-means clustering. For each image in the training data, SURF features are extracted and then quantized to the obtained K-means (the visual words). Then a histogram of visual word occurrences that represent that image is encoded.

The histograms of the training data are used to train a classifier called Support Vector Machine (SVM). That classifier is used during system deployment to classify the histograms obtained for test images.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

After the design, this system is implemented the face sketch image category classification methods based on the bag of visual words model. Exhaustive experimentation has been carried out on a set of sketch images. There is a configuration parameter for setting how much percentage of the data is considered as training data. But typically, 30% is found to be a reasonable value. 30% of images from each set are considered for the training data and the remainder, 70%, are considered for the validation data. The validation data are used to validate and set the different parameters of the system.

Table 1. Training Data Confusion Matrix for Face Shapes and Left Eyes

KNOWN	Face Shapes	Left Eyes
Face Shapes	1.00	0.00
Left Eyes	0.00	1.00

Average accuracy is 1.00. The training and validation average accuracy is 0.99985.

This table shows the confusion matrix resulted when inputting the training data such as face shapes and left eyes to be tested with the system. In this table, face shapes is known to be face shapes was 100%, left eyes is known to be left eyes was also 100%. The error rates was 0% in the training data confusion matrix. Both of the two sets of training and validation average accuracy result into average classification accuracy is 99.985%.

Table 2. Validation Data Confusion Matrix for Face Shapes and Left Eyes

KNOWN	Face Shapes	Left Eyes
Face Shapes	1.00	0.00
Left Eyes	0.50	0.50

Average accuracy is 0.75.

This table shows the confusion matrix for the validation data of face shapes and left eyes average accuracy of 75%. Table 1 captures 2400 of training images; 800 images for each selected classes for testing ('face shapes', 'left eyes') and 1200 images for random class that contains the mixing images of two categories / classes ('random_class'). The random images are shown in figure 5. In this table, although, face shapes is known to be face shapes was 100%, left eyes is known to be left eyes was decreased to 50%. The error rates was 50% in the training data confusion matrix. So, the validation average accuracy was also dropped out.

Figure 5. My Collected Test Data for Face Shapes and Left Eyes

Table 3. Test Data Confusion Matrix for Face Shapes and Left Eyes

KNOWN	Face Shapes	Left Eyes
Face Shapes	1.00	0.00
Left Eyes	0.50	0.50

Average accuracy is 0.75.

The test accuracy is 0.75.

Table 3 shows the confusion matrix of the collected test data. Average accuracy of 75% is achieved on the test data. Each image is classifier to the nearest class that looks most similar to it out of the two trained classes. In this table, although, face shapes is known to be face shapes was 100%, left eyes is known to be left eyes was decreased to 50%. The error rates was 50% in the training data confusion matrix. So, the validation average accuracy was also dropped out.

Table 4. Training Data Confusion Matrix for Hairs and Left Eyebrows

KNOWN	Hairs	Left Eyebrows
Hairs	1.00	0.00
Left Eyebrows	0.00	1.00

Average accuracy is 1.00. The training and validation average accuracy is 1.

This table shows the confusion matrix resulted when inputting the training data such as hairs and left eyebrows to be tested with the system. In this table, hairs is known to be hairs was 100%, left eyebrows is known to be left eyebrows was also 100%. The error rates was 0% in the training data confusion matrix. Both of the two sets of training and validation average accuracy result into average classification accuracy is 100%.

Table 5. Validation Data Confusion Matrix for Hairs and Left Eyebrows

KNOWN	Hairs	Left Eyebrows
Hairs	1.00	0.00
Left Eyebrows	0.50	0.50

Average accuracy is 0.75.

This table shows the confusion matrix for the validation data of hairs and left eyebrows average accuracy of 75%. Table 4 captures 2400 of training images; 800 images for each selected classes for testing ('hairs', 'left eyebrows') and 1200 images for random class that contains the mixing images of two categories / classes ('random_class'). The random images are shown in figure 6. In this table, although, hairs is known to be hairs was 100%, left eyebrows is known to be left eyebrows was decreased to 50%. The error rates was 50% in the training data confusion matrix. So, the validation average accuracy was also dropped out.

Figure 6. My Collected Test Data for Hairs and Left Eyebrows

Table 6. Test Data Confusion Matrix for Hairs and Left Eyebrows

KNOWN	Hairs	Left Eyebrows
Hairs	1.00	0.00
Left Eyebrows	0.50	0.50

Average accuracy is 0.75.

The test accuracy is 0.75.

Table 6 shows the confusion matrix of the collected test data. Average accuracy of 75% is achieved on the test data. Each image is classifier to the nearest class that looks most similar to it out of the two trained classes. In this table, although, hairs is known to be hairs was 100%, left eyebrows is known to be left eyebrows was decreased to 50%. The error rates was

50% in the training data confusion matrix. So, the validation average accuracy was also dropped out.

Table 7. Training Data Confusion Matrix for Noses and Mouths

KNOWN	Noses	Mouths
Noses	1.00	0.00
Mouths	0.00	1.00

Average accuracy is 1.00.

The training and validation average accuracy is 0.99881.

This table shows the confusion matrix resulted when inputting the training data such as noses and mouths to be tested with the system. In this table, noses is known to be noses was 100%, mouths is known to be mouths was also 100%. The error rates was 0% in the training data confusion matrix. Both of the two sets of training and validation average accuracy result into average classification accuracy is 99.881%.

Table 8. Validation Data Confusion Matrix for Noses and Mouths

KNOWN	Noses	Mouths
Noses	0.00	1.00
Mouths	0.50	0.50

Average accuracy is 0.25.

This table shows the confusion matrix for the validation data of noses and mouths average accuracy of 25%. Table 7 captures 2400 of training images; 800 images for each selected classes for testing ('noses', 'mouths') and 1200 images for random class that contains the mixing images of two categories / classes ('random_class'). The random images are shown in figure 7. In this table, although, noses is known to be noses was 100%, mouths is known to mouths was decreased to 50%. The error rates was 50% in the training data confusion matrix. So, the validation average accuracy was also dropped out.

Figure 7. My Collected Test Data for Noses and Mouths

Table 9. Test Data Confusion Matrix for Noses and Mouths

KNOWN	Noses	Mouths
Noses	0.00	1.00
Mouths	0.50	0.50

Average accuracy is 0.25.

The test accuracy is 0.25.

Table 9 shows the confusion matrix of the collected test data. Average accuracy of 25% is achieved on the test data. Each image is classifier to the nearest class that looks most similar to it out of the two trained classes. In this table, although, noses is known to be noses was 100%, mouths is known to mouths was decreased to 50%. The error rates was 50% in the training data confusion matrix. So, the validation average accuracy was also dropped out.

Figure 8. Classification results of images

This figure shows the images after classification. All classified images are grouped according to their category names.

Figure 9. Graphical analysis of data confusion matrix values for classification of Face Shapes and Left Eyes sketch images

The average classification accuracy of face shapes and left eyes for training data, validation data and testing data are calculated in table 1, table 2 and table 3 in detail. Figure 9 shows the graphical analysis of data confusion matrix for face shapes and left eyes after getting these average accuracy values from table 1, table 2 and table 3.

Figure 10. Graphical analysis of data confusion matrix values for classification of Hairs and Left Eyebrows sketch images

The average classification accuracy of hairs and left eyebrows for training data, validation data and testing data are calculated in table 4, table 5 and table 6 in detail. Figure 10 shows the graphical analysis of data confusion matrix for face shapes and left eyes after getting these average accuracy values from table 4, table 5 and table 6.

Figure 11. Graphical analysis of data confusion matrix values for classification of Noses and Mouths sketch images

The average classification accuracy of noses and mouths for training data, validation data and testing data are calculated in table 7, table 8 and table 9 in detail. Figure 11 shows the graphical analysis of data confusion matrix for noses and mouths after getting these average accuracy values from table 7, table 8 and table 9.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This system is implemented to become face sketch construction system, so, the accuracy of this categorization system is important. During experiment, it is found that the system with 2400 training images, 800 testing images and 1200 random images for two groups category classification, the overall accuracy is 75%. The experiment with the same data amount, but with three groups or four groups for classification, the accuracy drops to under 15%.

Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) descriptor, Speeded Up Robust Feature (SURF), K-means clustering algorithm, Bag of Words (BoW) model and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier approaches are mainly used for image category classification process. Till now, the system can only classify two groups between six groups to get a better accuracy. The weak point of the system is that if the system implements three groups, four groups or many groups instead of two groups for this category classification process, the performance of data values must be inaccurate and the classification images may not correct.

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